

REINFORCING

Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open
Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance

D7.1 – Data Management Plan

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The REINFORCING Data Management Plan (DMP) is the Deliverable 7.1 (D7.1) from the coordination and support action (CSA) REINFORCING project – Grant Agreement (GA) no. 101094435.

This deliverable introduces the first version of the DMP. The DPM provides procedures for data collection and describes policies for management, storage, organization, permissions and architecture security of the data generated by the project.

This DMP reflects the current state of the art of the REINFORCING project. However, the details and the final number of datasets may vary during the research project. The variations will be recorded in updated versions of this DMP.

PROJECT BACKGROUND

REINFORCING aims to become the ORRI central point of knowledge and expertise that supports territories and institutions in fostering Fair Transitions governance by aligning with societal values, needs and expectations.

REINFORCING proposes a novel approach to the development of a **One-Stop Source of expertise and services** on ORRI that will efficiently support institutional and territorial changes through:

A demand-driven strategy, involving a vast community of both experienced actors (i.e. project partners, advisory board members, grantee frontrunners and past and ongoing ORRI projects) as well as territories and institutions that are still at early stages of opening up to society. The REINFORCING community will take an inclusive approach to addressing gaps emerging from the observation of over 10 years of FP7 and H2020 funding programmes, such as the scarce involvement of the private sector and Balkans territories. The community will both benefit from REINFORCING services and expertise, and actively contribute to their identification and co-design.

A cooperative approach that capitalizes on existing experiences, tools, resources and joint forces with other ongoing projects for topic-specific expertise. ORRI is facing a shift from dedicated funding programmes (such as SwafS) to mainstreaming into R&I processes to address current climate and health challenges (e.g. EU Missions). Rather than reinventing the wheel, REINFORCING will build on the current ORRI knowledge base and inspiring examples, through a wide network of collaborations and reflexivity and adaptation of partners' expertise.

A sustainable long-term vision to guarantee ORRI uptake in future products and services beyond the duration of the project. H2020 projects have shown that ORRI initiatives are often strongly dependent on EU funding and territorial support is still limited. REINFORCING will provide such territories and their stakeholders with long-awaited tools to assess the benefits of ORRI practices, as well as their costs and necessary skills. This will strengthen Europe's know-how on ORRI within quadruple-helix institutions (academia, policy makers, industries and civil society), empowering territories beyond the project duration. A carefully planned and socially just business plan will ensure that the REINFORCING One-Stop Source keeps supporting territories in the long term.

1 DATA SUMMARY

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

At this stage of the project, it is very likely that no existing data will be reused.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Type of data

Personal data

- Name
- Affiliation
- Mailing address
- Gender
- Photo
- Video
- Audio (voice)

Other data

- Data from workshops in person and online (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6)
- Data from interviews (WP1 and WP5)

Formats of the data

- Data and metadata will be requested, stored and transferred in comma-separated values CSV format.
- To facilitate the data exchange, MS Excel compatible files including comma separated and .xls(x) format will also be accepted.
- For statistical purposes, other formats include .sas7bdat (SAS), .RData (R), .SAV (SPSS), .mat (matlab).
- Where applicable data formats may be migrated when new technologies become available and are proved robust enough to ensure digital continuity and continued availability of data.

What is the purpose of the data generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

In the context of the REINFORCING project, data generation serves specific purposes related to the project objectives.

The primary purpose of data collection and generation in REINFORCING is to develop a comprehensive and centralized source of expertise and services related to Open Research and Innovation (ORRI).

By gathering data on ORRI facilitators and ambassadors, the project aims to create a one-stop platform that offers efficient support for institutional and territorial transformations. This data will be used to establish a virtual map incorporated into the platform, providing information about entities with experience in supporting institutions and territories in ORRI grounding (Task 4.2).

Another objective of the REINFORCING project is to assess the impact of cascading grants and peer-learning activities. The data collection will involve a selected number of cascading grant recipients (5-10). The data will be collected through an online survey designed and implemented by Fraunhofer, and the subsequent analysis will be structured based on different territories and types of institutions involved (Task 5.2)

What is the origin/provenance of the data generated?

Origin of the data:

- Data from sign-up sheets/online forms at project workshops/training
- Personal data upon requests of the consortium
- Data from calls applications
- Data from questionnaires
- Data from interviews
- Data from REINFORCING community

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

ORRI research community

2 FAIR DATA

This DMP follows EU guidelines¹ and describes data management procedures according to FAIR² principles. The acronym FAIR stands for “findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable”, and describes data management practices that allow maximum knowledge circulation and return on investment.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

A persistent identifier must identify each and every dataset published on the REINFORCING project. REINFORCING will use Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), which are persistent identifiers

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?

Yes, all published data must contain the following obligatory metadata:

- title
- description
- author
- date modified
- version
- URL in the form of a DOI

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes, keywords will be provided for optimizing possibility for re-use.

Naming conventions.

Project deliverables are assigned a unique identifier REINFORCING_[number of Deliverable]_[date of submission], e.g. REINFORCING_D8.1_31012023 (already submitted).

All files made publicly available reference REINFORCING in their name, e.g.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

²<https://force11.org/info/guiding-principles-for-findable-accessible-interoperable-and-re-usable-data-publishing-version-b1-0/>

REINFORCING_XXXXXXX_[date], where XXXXXXX is a meaningful short description of the file.

Photographs and audio/visual recordings are be named REINFORCING_[event]_[date of event]_[description of event/photograph content, e.g. workshop].

2.2 Making data accessible

- Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes, the data will be deposited in a trusted repository: Zenodo.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

A REINFORCING community on Zenodo has been already created: <https://zenodo.org/communities/reinforcingproject/?page=1&size=20>

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes it does by assigning DOIs.

- Data:

Will all data be made openly available?

All data is forecast to be made openly available. The only data which will not be made openly accessible will be data which contains personally identifiable information and data underlying deliverables that are covered by confidentiality.

The personal data processed in the project are not made publicly accessible but kept closed and inaccessible to third parties.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

No embargo is expected at the moment.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Data will be published using standard file formats (txt, pdf, csv etc.). All data will be accessed using standard tools. Software relevant to access the data would be made available, but it is not seen as being a requirement. Should it be needed we will provide the required open source to access and analyze the data.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

No restriction on the use of the data exists, apart from giving the appropriate credit to the data creator as per the Creative Common chosen licenses.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

There is no need for a data access committee.

-Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes metadata will be openly available and will contain information to enable the user to access the data.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Data is expected to remain available indefinitely especially for what concerns data published in trusted repositories. Should the data be made unavailable, then metadata should still be available.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Documentation and reference to data processing software will be necessary and included.

2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

In the project we use standard file formats as noted above. Every dataset will have standard Zenodo metadata.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes, published datasets will include qualified references.

2.4 Increase data re-use

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

All datasets published in the REINFORCING project are made freely available and licensed under Creative Commons.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

All Personal Identifiable Information will be restricted to internal usage and not going to be shared with third parties. For shared information, standard format,

open source software, and proper documentation will guarantee re-usability by third parties.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The documentation and metadata of each dataset will report the data provenance through proper citation of the source of information using the formats usually accepted by the relevant scientific community.

3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

Costs for making data fair are estimated to be zero. Zenodo is funded by the EU, which means archiving data in this repository will be free of charge.

Consortium partners will use their own budgets to archive personal data in their own repositories.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Each beneficiary leading Work Packages is responsible for preparing the datasets to make FAIR the data collected within its own activities, provided that FGB, as Project Coordinator is co-responsible for general coordination and supervision. Furthermore, consortium partners have the responsibility to make sure their activities are in line with all applicable local, government and international laws, regulations and guidelines.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Data published on Zenodo stays indefinitely.

4 DATA SECURITY

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)? Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

The selected data repositories guarantee the enduring protection and security of public data. Zenodo commits to preserving items for as long as the repository exists. In the event of closure, every attempt will be made to transfer all content to appropriate alternative institutional or subject-based repositories. Moreover, data is securely backed up locally and in the cloud by the data-collecting partner. The retrieval of data is facilitated by the existing commercial cloud storage solution designed for backups.

5 ETHICS

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Deliverables D8.1, D8.2, D8.3 and D8.4 cover the ethics requirements in connection with the main issues of data management within the project.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Yes, an informed consent for data sharing for research only purpose (within the REINFORCING project activities context) and long term preservation will be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data.